

ATTEMPTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF CONIFERIN

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The glucoside, coniferin (I: R=H; R₁=CH₂OH), was first isolated from the sap of the cambium of Coniferae by Tiemann and Harmann (*Ber.*, 1874, 7, 611) who showed that it was a β-d-glucoside of coniferyl alcohol.

Pauly and Feurstein (*Ber.*, 1927, 60, 1031) claimed to have synthesised the glucoside by a biochemical method, although they failed to synthesise it by a purely chemical method. Attempts have therefore been made to synthesise coniferin by steps involving standard chemical reactions.

Thus, methyl ferulate, prepared by an improved method, was condensed with O-tetra-acetyl-α-d-glucosidyl bromide in aqueous-alkali-acetone when the hitherto unreported methyl-3-methoxy-4-tetra-acetyl-β-d-glucosidoxy-cinnamate (I:R = Ac; R₁ = -CO₂Me) was obtained in good yield. Attempts to reduce the ester group of the foregoing compound with lithium-aluminium hydride, with a view to obtaining coniferin, however, unaccountably failed although varying conditions for reduction were employed; the starting material was invariably recovered unchanged in each case.

The following improved procedure was adopted in which the conversion of acetoferuloyl chloride to the corresponding ester proceeded with simultaneous deacetylation to yield methyl ferulate.

(a). A mixture of 4-acetylferuloyl chloride (9.6 g.) (Fosdick and Starke, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 3353), methyl alcohol (40 c.c.) and pyridine (9 drops) was refluxed for 3 hours; excess methyl alcohol was distilled off and water added when a brown oil separated which thickened on cooling in a refrigerator. The water was decanted and the thick oil was taken up in ether; the ethereal solution was washed with water, dried (MgSO₄) and the ether evaporated. The gummy residue on distillation under reduced pressure (2.9 mm/180-90°, bath temp.) afforded a yellow viscous oil which, on keeping in the refrigerator for a week, deposited at places rosettes of needles; when rubbed with a glass rod and left in the refrigerator overnight, methyl ferulate solidified to a thick paste of crystalline needles, which were crystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 65°, yield 4.8 g.

(b). Pyridine (3 drops) was added with shaking to acetoferuloyl chloride (1.0 g.), suspended in methyl alcohol (5 c.c.), when the reaction mixture became warm and part of the acid chloride went into solution. After a few minutes, the whole mixture solidified to a thick paste of crystals. An additional quantity of methyl alcohol (5 c.c.)

and pyridine (3 drops) were added and warmed gently for 2-3 minutes until a clear solution was obtained. On keeping, the solution deposited crystalline methyl acetoferulate which on recrystallisation from methyl alcohol yielded the pure specimen (0.8 g), m.p. 122°. Deacetylation was effected by boiling with MeOH-HCl (conc.) (4 drops) for ten minutes and the oil, obtained after evaporating the excess methyl alcohol, deposited methyl ferulate, when nucleated with the specimen obtained in expt. (a). Crystallised from methyl alcohol, it melted at 65°.

Acetylation of methyl ferulate with acetic anhydride-pyridine on a water-bath for one hour yielded methyl acetoferulate, m.p. and mixed m.p. 123°.

Methyl 3-Methoxy-4-tetra-acetyl-β-D-glucosidoxycinnamate (I: R=Ac; R₁=CO₂Me). —O-Tetra-acetyl-2-D-glucosidyl bromide (6.3 g.) in acetone (50 c.c.) was added to methyl ferulate (4.5 g.), dissolved in aqueous caustic soda (0.9 g in 27 c.c. water) and the homogeneous red solution was set aside for 16 hours at the room temperature. It was then extracted with benzene (30 c.c. × 3), the combined extract washed with water (60 c.c.) containing NaOH (2 drops; 2N) and then with water (60 c.c. × 3), dried (CaCl₂), filtered and the benzene removed under reduced pressure. The viscous oily residue was dissolved in the minimum quantity of methyl alcohol by warming; on keeping in the refrigerator, the solution deposited white shining needles which after three recrystallisations from methyl alcohol yielded the pure *glucoside*, m.p. 140°, yield 4.25 g. (Found: C, 55.8; H, 5.3. C₂₅H₃₀O₁₃ requires C, 55.76; H, 5.57%). $[\alpha]_D^{25} = -31.08$ (c in CHCl₃, 0.0458).

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